

Feed and Pasture Management Practices of Dairy Farms in Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar

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Abstract

Myanmar has potential for the development of the livestock sector, particularly in the dairy sector. Pasture enables the farmers to reduce the cost of producing milk through better forage and its quality. However, most of the dairy farms do not get aware of the role of pasture in dairy farming, and no information on pasture is documented in Myanmar. The milk is primarily produced in Mandalay region, Yangon region, and around the capital Naypyitaw. The study was carried out to observe feed and pasture management systems of dairy farms in Nay Pyi Taw. A total of twenty dairy farms including almost all of the middle scale dairy farms around Nay Pyi Taw area were surveyed in 2019-2020 to observe the feed and pasture management practices in the farms. The dairy farms relied on agricultural by-products and feed concentrates. Agricultural by-products were purchased and stored in advance in the farms to overcome feed shortage during the dry period. Most of the farms used more concentrate ratio in the feed ration. Roughage-concentrate ratio should be adjusted with improved quality pasture to reduce feed cost in the farms. Although pasture was grown in a few farms, it was cultivated in small areas with poor agronomic practices. Fodder scarcity is one of the major constraints, and limitations for pasture cultivation in the farms were lack of access to improved pasture varieties, poor knowledge on pasture cultivation, and water scarcity. Feed availability and quality should be improved by using improved pasture cultivars with suitable agronomic practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Myanmar is an agricultural country and more than 70% of population lives in the rural areas [1]. Almost those people are depending on agricultural activities, livestock breeding, fishing and forest products for their livelihood. Most rural households raise livestock which supports the farm economy through draught power and by-products [2]. In 2018, the share of the GDP contribution from the livestock and fishery sector in Myanmar was approximately 10.2 percent [3] and it is generally under producing because of insufficient feed quality, quantity and management. However, there is a great potential to increase food security and food quality in cattle and other livestock industries in Myanmar. As the economy of Myanmar develops, its cattle industry is growing and transitioning from a draft-based use to a more meat animal-focused market [4].

The Myanmar dairy sector is a sector at early stages of development [5]. Milk is primarily produced in three regions: Mandalay region, Yangon region, and around the capital Naypyitaw [6]. Dairy cattle feeding system requires good quality forage as basic feed with concentrates as supplements [7], and sustainability of production in dairy farms can be achieved by better feeding. Improved pasture plays very important role as it provides a major source of

feed for dairy cows and it should be grown widely to raise dairy production. Understanding the practices in dairy farms is prerequisite to help enhanced dairy farming. However, there is less documentation on feed and pasture management practices of dairy farms in Myanmar. Therefore, the present study was carried out to observe feed and pasture management practices of dairy farms in Nay Pyi Taw.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted during 2019-2020 in Nay Pyi Taw Council area. A total of 20 dairy farms from Zayarthiri, Pobbathiri, Tatkon and Pyinmana Township were selected by purposive random sampling based on the secondary data gathered from Livestock, Breeding, Veterinary Department (LBVD). The categories of the survey data were: (a) dairy farm description, (b) feed and pasture management practices, (c) average milk production, and (d) constraints in dairy farms. The data were analyzed by descriptive statistics using Microsoft Excel Program.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Cattles in the Dairy Farms of the Study Area

Two types of cattle were observed as local and *Friesians bred* in the dairy farms. Every farm reared Friesians bred cows and 30.0% of dairy farms owned Myanmar local cows (Table 1) for other purposes. The total cattle of the dairy farms ranged from 9 to 185 with the average number about 66.4 (Table 1). There was the average number of about 25.1 lactating cows in the range of 4 to 95 numbers. Among the surveyed dairy farms, some farms were commercial dairy farms such as Funhua, Super Cow, Aung Chanthar, San Waddy, Unison, Mahar Nwe, etc, and they possessed many cattle. There were also 13.6 numbers of heifers in average in the dairy farms, ranging from 0 to 50 numbers. Calf is the young cattle and there was averagely 16.8 calves ranging from 2 to 59 numbers. In the study area, it was observed that there were some bulls ranging 0 to 20. Bulls were used to breed dairy cows with lower cost in most of the dairy farms. However, some farms did not rear bulls at all and they used artificial insemination (AI) method to breed highly productive dairy cows.

Table 1: Description of the cattle in the dairy farms of Nay Pyi Taw

		Respondent dairy farms (N=20)	
		Frequency (no.)	%
Friesian bred		20	100.0
Local		6	30.0
	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Lactating cow	25.1±21.9	4	95

Heifer	13.6±13.7	0	50
Calf	16.8±16.7	2	59
Bull	2.6±4.4	0	20
Local	5.95±18.7	0	80
Total cattle	66.4±60.0	9	185

3.2 Feed Management Practices for Dairy Cattle

Feeding management system is very important for dairy farms to produce sustainable high milk yield. Various kinds of feed stuff were observed to feed cattle in the surveyed farms (Table 2). Roughages used in the surveyed farms were rice straw, sorghum stover, grass and vegetable leaf waste. All the surveyed farms (100%) used rice straw to feed the cattle and straw was not added any treatment. Rice straw is poor in nutritive value containing very low protein [8], and feeding of high quality hay is in practice in the developed countries. Most of the farms fed sorghum stover (65%) and grass (85%) to the cattles. A few farms (10%) collected vegetable leaf waste such as cabbage leaf from the markets and places of loading cabbages onto the vehicles for transportation, to feed the cattles. Rice straw was available from the rice cultivation area such as Yezin (25%), Pyinmana (25%), Leway (25%) and surrounding places (50%) (Table 3). Some farms managed to get roughage by cultivating sorghum and some farms cultivated pasture grass in few acres or cut the grass from roadside or other common land.

Dairy farmers provided feed to dairy cows not only roughage but also feed concentrates. The term concentrate refers to that group of feeds which are relatively high in total digestible nutrients and low in crude fibre. It was found that various feed supplements were used by the dairy farms (Table 2). In the surveyed farms, all respondent dairy farmers (100%) fed pulses grain powder, and each 50% of the respondent farms used rice bran, broken rice, pulses crop residue as supplement feed concentrate. Some farms provided cotton seed cake (40%), sesame cake (30%), brewers grain (30%), corn seed (20%) and pellet (20%). Few farmers can afford to purchase expensive pellet for supplement concentrates. These feed stuffs were available from Tatkon (25% of the respondents), Pyinmana (35% of the respondents) and far distance locations such as Mandalay (30% of the respondents), Meiktila (45% of the respondents) and Yangon (20% of the respondents) (Table 3).

Feed rations were varied with dairy cattle in the farms. In this study, ration to a lactating cow was discussed and it was fed with the average feed rate of 18.3 kg roughage ranging from 11 kg to 30 kg and 11.2 kg feed concentrate with the range of 6 kg to 28.6 kg (Table 4). Most of the farms seemed to rely on feed concentrates because majority of roughages was low quality rice straw. In these farms, the average ratio of roughage and concentrate was about 60% : 40 % (w/w) making the feed cost higher and less profitability. The average milk yield of a cow in the dairy farms was about 11.6 litres per day in the range of 4 litres to 16 litres. Forage and concentrate ratio above 80:20 can support about 20 litres (20 kg or about 12 viss) of milk yield

if roughage quality is good [9]. Thus, roughage-concentrate ratio of the studied farms should be adjusted with improved quality pasture to reduce feed cost in the farms.

Table 2: Proportion of dairy farms using different types of feeds for dairy cattle in Nay Pyi Taw

Variable	Respondent dairy farms (N=20)	
	Frequency (no.)	%
<u>Roughage</u>		
Rice straw	20	100.00
Sorghum stover	13	65.00
Grass	17	85.00
Vegetable leaf waste	2	10.00
<u>Feed concentrate</u>		
Rice bran	10	50.00
Broken rice	10	50.00
Pulses crop residues	10	50.00
Pulses grain powder	20	100.00
Cotton seed cake	8	40.00
Sesame cake	6	30.00
Brewers grain	6	30.00
Corn seed	4	20.00
Pellet	4	20.00

Table 3: Proportion of dairy farms with various access of feed stuff for their cattle in Nay Pyi Taw

Variable	Respondent dairy farms (N=20)	
	Frequency (no.)	%
<u>Location for roughage (rice straw) source</u>		
Yezin	5	25.00

Pyinmana	5	25.00
Leway	4	20.00
Surrounding places	10	50.00
<u>Location for protein concentrate source</u>		
Tatkon	5	25.00
Pyinmana	7	35.00
Mandalay	6	30.00
Meiktilar	9	45.00
Yangoon	4	20.00

Table 4: Feed rates and milk yield of a lactating cow in the dairy farms (N=20) of Nay Pyi Taw

Variables	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
roughage rate (kg)	18.3 ± 6.1	11	30
concentrate rate (kg)	11.2 ± 5.2	6	28.6
milk yield/cow/day (litre)	11.6 ± 3.2	4	16

3.3 Fodder and Pasture Crops

Among the surveyed dairy farms, 70% of the farms managed to get fodder by cultivating some sort of fodder crops such as sorghum, corn, cowpea and pasture grass but 30% of the farms did not grow any fodder crop (Figure 1) as they were living in the urban area and they had no land for fodder cultivation. Pasture is important feed source for dairy cattle as it contains high nutritive value. The pasture grasses cultivated in the surveyed farms were Napier, Ruzi and Para. Among the pasture varieties, Napier was cultivated in almost all (93%) of the fodder cultivated farms and a few farms grow Para (21%) and Ruzi (7.1%) in very small area of the fodder cultivated farms. In the Napier grown farms, Napier was cut at about 4 months or the height of higher than human height (Plate 1) indicating that it was cut at improper growth stage for fodder. Napier grass is a robust perennial grass grown for forage mainly in tropical areas of America, Asia, South and Central America. Napier grass is easy to establish and persistent, drought tolerant, suitable for cutting and very good for silage making. It is a high yielding fodder crop with good palatability, highly nutritious especially at the young stage. Napier can grow on almost any soil. However, it should be cut at 40-45 days interval. It reduced quality and palatability as it matures [10]. Para and Ruzi are softer than Napier. Although there was other improved pasture grasses such as Mombasa, Cayman and Mulato II which are suitable for tropical, any farm did not grow these grasses yet. Therefore, this result highlighted

the improved pasture cultivars are needed to grow in the dairy farms and many research regarding pasture crops are being demanded to improve feed availability.

Figure 1: Fodder cultivation and fodder crops grown in the dairy farms of Nay Pyi Taw

Plate.1 Cutting Napier grass at improper growth stage in a dairy farm of Nay Pyi Taw

3.4 Pasture Management

Although pasture is not demanding much fertilizer like food crops, it requires some amount of nutrient, particularly nitrogen, for sustainable forage production throughout the year. Only some percentage of pasture grown dairy farms applied chemical fertilizer such as urea and compound fertilizer to pasture field and all the farms (100%) applied cow dung of the cattle as farmyard manure (FYM) to their pasture field (Figure 2). Napier grown without any input

of manure or fertilizer produced very short plants, and it reduced number of tillers which might be due to insufficient availability of nutrients [11].

If pasture can be irrigated, forage can be produced during even the dry season. Most of the farms afforded to irrigate their pasture field using tube well but some farms cannot. Most of the respondent farms (77.8%) irrigated their pasture fields but only small area was irrigated. The other farms (22.2%) did not irrigate and they cultivated crops only in rainy season such as sorghum, corn and cowpea for fodder. Irrigation not only increases forage yields but also provides greater reliability of production with less year-to-year variability [11]. Therefore, fertilization and irrigation are important for pasture cultivation and dairy farming. Moreover, the systematic rotation of cutting plot by plot is important for sustaining forage yield with high nutritive value. Only 21% of the pasture grown dairy farms said they practiced rotation of cutting and most of the farms cut the pasture at their convenience. It indicates the needs of farmers' awareness on the relationship of forage quality and maturity stage. Overall, pasture should be grown enough for the dairy farms with systematic agronomic management.

Figure 2: Pasture management in the dairy farms of Nay Pyi Taw

3.5 Total Farm Area and Pasture Grown Area

The average dairy farm area was 23.5 acres ranging from 0.11 acres to 130 acres (Table 5). Some farms were with small area as these farms were in urban area and some farms were in large area as the farmers can hire the land from the government with long term grant. The land required for the construction of dairy sheds and ancillary structures including maternity pens, straw store, feed store, implements room, milk room, chaff cutter shed, manure pit, roads and alleys and office etc. Although there was more land to grow fodder and pasture in most of the farms, the cultivated area for forage was averagely 5.3 acres including pasture grass area 4 acres ranging from 0 to 15 acres (Table 5). It showed that the pasture grown area was small as compared to total farm area. If other situations are favorable for growing pasture, pasture growing area should be extended in the farms.

Table 5: Total farm area and fodder grown area of the dairy farms in Nay Pyi Taw

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Total farm area (ac.)	23.5 ± 33.8	0.11	130.0
Total fodder grown area (ac.)	5.3 ± 7.4	0	29.0
Pasture grass area (ac.)	4.0 ± 5.0	0	15.0

3.6 LIMITATIONS FOR GROWING PASTURE

There were limitations for growing pasture in the dairy farms of the study area (Figure 3). Lack of access to improved pasture varieties, poor knowledge on technology regarding pasture cultivation and its management were the limitations that were commonly experienced by most dairy farmers. Water scarcity is one of the limitations for growing pasture extensively in the dairy farms. Pasture cannot be grown extensively throughout the year without sufficient water sources. Another limitation was no land for pasture growing for the small dairy farms that were situated in urban areas. These farmers were also poor resource persons who cannot afford to get the land tenure permission from the government as the large farms included in this survey. The survey result pointed out that it is needed to get awareness on pasture improvement strategy by the various stakeholders, such as pasture research and development, education programs to farmers, and support of public and private sector to improve pasture development.

Figure 3: Limitations for growing pasture in the dairy farms of Nay Pyi Taw

3.7 Constraints for the Dairy Farms

Low investment, small land area, lack of high cross breed dairy cows, feed shortage, water scarcity, labor shortage, market condition and livestock health were the constraints experienced by 10%, 30%, 20%, 60%, 15%, 5%, 15%, and 20% respectively of the respondent farms (Figure 4). Among the constraints, feed shortage was commonly experienced by 60% of the respondent farms. They said that the feed abundant period was rainy season and feed shortage was during dry period. They generally overcome this issue by purchasing roughage,

particularly rice straw, and stored in advance. Practically to solve the feed shortage is to grow improved pasture.

The 20 % of dairy farms said that the lack of high cross breed dairy cows was a constraint for dairy farms in the study area. Although some farms afforded artificial insemination (AI) method, some farms used natural breeding with bull in the farm. Artificial insemination offers several potential advantages over natural breeding. Similarly, livestock health problem was one of the constraints in the dairy farms. These two problems can be solved with the kind help of LBVD.

Small land area was also a constraint reported by the small farms. The Government sector established livestock zone in Nay Pyi Taw Council area by allotting the land with long term grant. Poor resource person cannot afford to get the land to extend their farms or establish the improved dairy farms. Even the farms in this zone could not establish pasture oriented dairy farms because of water scarcity. All livestock operations require ample water supplies to support the intended livestock herd. Water is important in dairy farm to clean cattle and to grow pasture. Pasture can be highly productive with proper irrigation throughout the year. Apart from increased yields, irrigation provides greater reliability of production with less year-to-year variability [12] and improved quality of products. The solutions for water scarcity in the dairy farms should be considered to develop the dairy farms.

Figure 4: Constraints for the dairy farms in Nay Pyi Taw

3.8 Dairy Products of the Dairy Farms

Many dairy products such as cheese, butter, yogurt, condensed milk, pasteurized milk can be produced from the milk. However, all the farms (100 %) sold as fresh milk to tea shops and bakeries around Nay Pyi Taw and only two kinds of value added products (Pasteurized milk and yogurt) were produced by some farms (25% and 35 %, respectively) (Table 6). It reflects production of value added dairy products was still under developed probably due to poor technology, low investment, unstable electricity, market and lower inputs in dairy

industry. The limitations for producing various dairy products may be lack of technology, low investment and machines, unstable electricity, market competition from imported dairy products. To develop the dairy sector, these limitations should be considered to solve in public and private.

Table 6: Milk products produced by the dairy farms in Nay Pyi Taw

Dairy products	Respondent farms (N=20)	
	Frequency (no.)	%
Fresh milk	20	100.00
Pasteurized milk	5	25.00
Yogurt	7	35.00

4. CONCLUSION

The average total herd size of the surveyed farms was about 66 cattle ranging from at least 9 to 185 numbers in the average farm size of 23 acres. The dairy farms relied on agricultural by-products and feed concentrates. They overcome feed shortage during the dry period by purchasing and stored straw in advance for their cattle. Most of the farms used more concentrate ratio in the feed ration. Roughage-concentrate ratio should be adjusted with improved quality pasture to reduce feed cost in the farms. Although some pasture cultivars were grown in some dairy farms, not enough pasture area was being cultivated with poor agronomic practices. Improved pasture cultivars were needed to grow with suitable agronomic practices in the farms. Fodder scarcity is one of the major constraints in dairy farms, and limitations for pasture cultivation in most farms were lack of access to improved pasture varieties, poor knowledge on pasture cultivation, and water scarcity. Production of value added dairy products of the dairy farms in Nay Pyi Taw was still under developed. The introduction, research and extension regarding suitable improved pasture varieties and management system should be conducted to develop feed availability and quality, and ultimately, this report would help in decision making to select the prioritization to improve the dairy sector.

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